

Implications of Average Momentum On Quantum Bound State Behaviour

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In a previous note (1) we argued that the translational generator d/dx being associated with momentum (px) already appears in Fermat's principle for both reflection and refraction. We suggested that d/dx is linked to an invariant spatial variable which in turn is associated with momentum conservation in the same direction. This may be written as: $d/dx (px)x = (px)$. Alternatively $(px)x = -i \ln(\exp(i px x))$ with $\exp(i px x)$ being a directional probability distribution (i.e. values for p and $-p$ differ) and $\ln(\exp(i px x))$ being of the form of information in information theory.

One may then ask: How does one link average momentum in the case of a bound state with a potential $V(x)$? In general, such a bound system is solved using the time-independent Schrodinger equation i.e. conservation of energy using d/dx twice and a p (rms) not a p average obtain from $-i d/dx \ln(W) = p(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction and $p_{ave} = W dW/dx$. After all, the form $\exp(i (px) x)$ may be obtained from considerations of d/dx and p , not energy conservation (even though $E=pc$ for light).

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a directional probability. If both p and $-p$ are present then: $p \exp(ipx) - p \exp(-ipx)$ is not zero because the spatial probability distinguishes between the two. Only by multiplying $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ does one remove motion. If p and $-p$ are present, however, as in an OR situation, i.e. $\exp(ipx) + \exp(-ipx)$, then it is as if the particle is bound or localized and $P(p,x)+P(-p,x) = C \cos(px)$.

We consider the two components of $\exp(ipx)$ in: $\int dx \cos(px) \sin(px)$. Why does this equal 0 from a momentum perspective? $\sin(px) = 1/p d/dx \cos(px)$. Thus the integral is: $\int dx \{ P(p)+P(-p) \} \text{momentum}(P(p)+P(-p))$ } or the average momentum at x . Overall the particle is bound and so there can be no momentum globally so the integral must be zero and hence $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ must be orthogonal over a period even though they represent the same p value.

This same idea holds for a linear combination of $\{P(p,x)+P(-p,x)\}$ sums for different p 's. (We consider overall positive or negative parity.) Thus: $\int dx W dW/dx = 0$ holds for even-odd reasons, but also for the physical overall zero momentum. Even with a potential present: $-i W W d/dx \ln(W) = P_{ave}(x)$. In other words, bound state quantum mechanics is linked to $W dW/dx$ integrating to 0 even though there are positive and negative pockets at various x values. This follows from the orthogonality of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ over a wavelength from a free particle which conserves momentum. This result holds for any $V(x)$ even though $V(x)$ fixes the coefficients of the linear combination of $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \{P(p,x)+P(-p,x)\}$ using energy considerations.

Zero average momentum follows from momentum conservation found in $\exp(i (px) x)$. In fact we have argued that the unusual probability wave form $\exp(i (px) x)$ exists to ensure constant momentum (momentum conservation) for a free particle.

We argue that considering average momentum equal to 0 overall leads to ideas of zero point energy, orthogonal energy states and a crest/trough pattern without considering the time-independent Schrodinger equation which is based on energy conservation. Thus we argue

that ideas related to d/dx and momentum carry over from Fermat's principle into a bound quantum state and its average momentum which is often not considered.

Bound State Considerations and Directional Probability

We have argued in (2) that a directional spatial probability $P(p,x)$ distinguishes forward and backwards motion i.e

$$P(p,x) \text{ is not equal to } P(-p,x) \quad ((1))$$

For an OR situation one cannot determine the direction of motion. Thus we suggest:

$$P(p,x) + P(-p,x) = F_{\text{even}}(p,x) \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Overall } P(p,x) = F_{\text{even}}(p,x) + C_1 B_{\text{odd}}(p,x) \quad ((3))$$

(There are reasons to believe that C_1 is proportional to the imaginary number i i.e. the condition that $P(p,x) dP(p,x)/dx = 0$ at each x , but we are not interested in behaviour at a point x in this note, but rather with bound states and average momentum.)

From Fermat's principle (1) we have argued that d/dx plays the role of a momentum operator. It may be applied to ((2)) to create an average momentum integral for a kind of bound state i.e. one with equal weights for p and $-p$ i.e. ((2)).

$$\text{Integral } F_{\text{even}}(p,x) d/dx F_{\text{even}}(p,x) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) equals 0 because of even-odd function considerations, but how does this relate to average momentum? For a bound state, average momentum in a range may be positive or negative, but the average must be zero because the particle is "bound" i.e. not moving overall to the right or left.

Thus ((4)) becomes the conservation of momentum statement for a bound system i.e. a combination of p and $-p$. This suggests fluctuation in the system even though the average momentum is zero. This we argue is important for ground state zero energy, but first we wish to generalize to more than one p .

Multiple p Values

In the above section we considered only p and $-p$. In the presence of a potential $V(x)$ for a bound state, one should have a variety of p and $-p$'s. In such a case, one may take a weighted average of $(P(p,x) + P(-p,x))$ values i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \{ P(p,x) + P(-p,x) \} \quad ((5))$$

We then calculate “average momentum” (not rms momentum from the time-independent Schrodinger equation).

$$\text{Average momentum} = \int dx W \frac{dW}{dx} = 0 \quad \text{by odd-even functions} \quad ((6))$$

Here we assume fixed parity for $\{P(p,x)+P(-p,x)\}$ e.g. either even or odd for all p.

$$\text{Then: } \int dx F_{\text{even}}(p_1,x) F_{\text{even}}(p_2,x) = 0 \quad ((7))$$

which distinguishes different momenta spatially overall x.

Thus average momentum at x, $W \frac{dW}{dx}$, must have regions of both positive and negative values even though the overall integral is zero. This we argue suggests fluctuation in the system.

Zero Point Energy

The simplest way for $\int dx W(x) \frac{dW}{dx} = 0$ (without $W(x)$ being a constant) is to have a single hump with a positive slope on one side of 0 and a symmetric negative value on the other. This suggests the particle is somewhat localized to $x=0$, but contains inner momentum pieces $F(x,p)$, $F(x,-p)$ and so its energy cannot be zero. This we argue fits the ground state energy of the quantum oscillator. Because we have probability density associated with motion $F(p,x)$ (for p and -p in an OR situation) then there is no zero energy solution.

One may ask: Why not simply use $\exp(ipx)$ with $p=0$ for an oscillator ground state for example. We note that a directional density $\exp(ipx)$ suggests a characteristic length called the wavelength proportional to $1/p$. If p becomes small, the wavelength increases. One cannot follow the particle's motion in time within this wavelength, but on average it obeys $p=\text{constant}$. Thus one needs to consider full units of half wavelengths for physical reasons. A very small p implies a very large box or very large turning points in the oscillator case. A low energy oscillator solution, however, has the opposite, namely turning points (classical) which define a very small length. Thus one may not use a tiny p in a small space to obtain an almost zero energy.

Crest/Trough Pattern

From the Fermat least time solution d/dx function = (px) with function = $(px) x = -i \ln(\exp(i px x))$ we see that $\exp(i px x)$ involves a set of crests and troughs in both $\cos((px)x)$ and $\sin((px)x)$. Furthermore $\cos((px)x)$ and $\sin((px)x)$ are orthogonal over x as suggested above. The form $W = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ in principle could be smooth, but $\int dx W \frac{dW}{dx}$ suggests that a set of crests or crest/trough pattern applies. This has implications for distinguishing spatially between different energies because W_n for an energy E_n should be orthogonal to W_{n+1} in space for E_{n+1} . Otherwise a low energy state cannot be distinguished from a higher energy one i.e. one could argue that a lower energy state contained part of a higher

energy one. Thus the form $\int dx W dW/dx=0$ leading to crests and troughs may resolve this issue. One may note that different $\exp(ipx)$ s are also orthogonal.

In fact if one uses conservation of energy using $-i\hbar d/dx$ as a p operator then:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad (8)$$

This leads automatically to orthogonal solutions mathematically, but we argue that the notion of average momentum equalling zero in a bound state already anticipates this for any potential. We also note that the idea of average zero energy also anticipates the ground state energy which also follows from (8).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the notion of directional density which follows from Fermat's principle: d/dx function = (px) so function = $(px)x = -i \ln(\exp(ipx x))$ with $\exp(i px x)$ being directional probability i.e. having different values for p and $-p$, has implications on a quantum bound state. For a bound state we consider p and $-p$ in an OR situation. This leads to an even function $\cos((px) x)$. We suggest that because Fermat's principle is linked with momentum conservation, notions of average momentum should carry over to a bound state which is traditionally described in terms of energy conservation i.e. Schrodinger's time-independent equation with a p rms (rather than a p ave) following from: $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W = p_{rms}^2 / 2m$.

We argue from general principles that: $\int \cos(px) \sin(px) dx = 0$ even if one does not know the explicit forms i.e. writes $P(p,x) = F_{even}(p,x) + C B_{odd}(p,x)$ i.e. $\int dx F dF/dx = 0$. We then suggest that for a bound state with a $V(x)$, there is a linear combination of $\{P(p,x) + P(-p,x)\}$ all with the same parity. $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) F(p,x)$ with $a(p)$ unknown implies that: $\int dx W dW/dx = \int dx F dF/dx$ is zero. This we argue suggests zero point energy for any $V(x)$ because the simplest solution is a crest which represents, for example, the ground state $W(x)$ of an oscillator. Furthermore a crest/trough pattern ensures that different energy solutions (linked to different numbers of crests/troughs) are orthogonal in space.

Thus we suggest that some properties of quantum bound states may be deduced without using the time-independent Schrodinger equation which is based on energy conservation, but by only considering average momentum which is 0 overall. This average momentum follows from the ideas of $d/dx (-i) \ln(\exp(ipx)) = p$ found in Fermat's theorem. {One may also note that: $-i d/dx \ln(W) = \langle p \rangle$ where $p_{ave} = \frac{1}{W} \int W \langle p \rangle W dx$. Thus, both the free particle and bound particle may be formulated in terms of the spatial derivative of information (from information theory) linked to momentum.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Association of X and P in Classical Physics and Information/Invariance Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2022)
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